

Determination of Malaria Prophylaxis in Experimentally Infected BALB/c Mice by Bioactive Constituents of an Alternative Medicinal Plant

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ABSTRACT

One of the strategies employed in malaria control and possible elimination efforts is the prevention of the establishment of malaria parasite infections using prophylactic antimalarial drugs. This strategy has been negatively affected by the development of resistance of the malaria parasite to the currently used antimalarial drugs. This development has increased the urgent need for new antimalarial compounds with prophylactic properties against malaria. This study was conducted to investigate the malaria prophylactic potential of bioactive compounds from extracts of *Alstonia boonei*, a medicinal plant traditionally used for malaria treatment in Nigeria and other African countries. The bioactive compounds were identified by Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometer analysis technique and then subjected to antimalarial tests to determine their prophylactic activity in mice experimentally infected with *Plasmodium berghei*. Results from the tests showed that the bioactive compounds possess significant dose-dependent prophylactic properties at $p < 0.05$ at the doses used. From these findings, it was concluded that the plant is a potential source of prophylactic antimalarial molecules and should be further studied for antimalarial drug development.

Keywords: Malaria, prophylaxis, experimentally infected, bioactive constituents, drug development

INTRODUCTION

Malaria is a fatal, insect-borne tropical disease caused by the *Plasmodium* parasite, and it is transmitted by the bite of the female *Anopheles* mosquito (Imieje and Amafile, 2025). Malaria continues to pose public health challenges globally and is a major cause of morbidity and mortality, especially in sub-Saharan Africa, where it is endemic (WHO, 2019). Malaria remains a major global public health problem, following the increasing resistance of the malaria parasite to the majority of antimalarial drugs currently in use (WHO, 2012). This development of resistance to commonly used antimalarial drugs is a threat to the efforts so far made to prevent and control malaria (WHO 2012). To effectively prevent and control malaria, there is a need for new antimalarial molecules with novel modes of action different from those of the

currently used drugs against the disease (Nanven *et al.*, 2024; WHO, 2019).

Natural products such as those from plants play important roles as leads for the discovery and development of new drugs (Madhiri and Vijayalakshini, 2018; Muhseen *et al.*, 2021). *Alstonia boonei* belongs to the family Apocynaceae and is an herbal medicinal plant of West African origin (Ogbuehi and Ebong, 2015). Parts of the plant are used in traditional alternative medicine for the treatment of many diseases, including malaria (Arise and Lawal, 2012).

Malaria prophylaxis is aimed at preventing the establishment of the *Plasmodium* parasite even when exposed to it by the bite of the female *Anopheles* mosquito that transmits it (WHO, 2019). The development of new and novel prophylactic

antimalarial molecules with novel modes of action will play key roles in malaria prevention and control (Madhiri and Vijayalakshini, 2018; WHO, 2019; Muhseen *et al.*, 2021). This present study is important because new molecules for the development of novel prophylactic medicines could come out of it, which would contribute immensely towards malaria prevention and control.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection, Authentication and Preparation of Plant Materials

The leaves, stem bark, and roots of *Alstonia boonei* were collected from Obukpa village in Nsukka Local Government Area in Enugu State, Nigeria. They were identified and authenticated by a botanist expert in the Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology, University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Enugu State, Nigeria. The plant parts were cut into small pieces, washed, and air dried for two weeks at room temperature. The dry samples were then ground into powder with a well-cleaned mechanical grinding machine (Afolabi and Abejide, 2020).

Aqueous Extraction

A measurement of 500 g each of the ground fine powder obtained from the leaves, stem bark, and roots was percolated in 1600 mL of water for 72h, after which it was filtered. This was followed by evaporating the filtrate collected to dryness using a temperature-regulated water bath pre-set at 40°C to yield the extract concentrate, which was stored in the refrigerator at 4°C before use in Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometer analysis (Amole and Ilori, 2010).

Ethanollic Extraction

Another 500 g each of the ground plant material (leaves, stem bark, and roots) powder was measured out and dispersed in 2.5 L of ethanol. The mixture was shaken with a mechanical shaking machine for 72 h, after which it was vacuum filtered. The resultant extract was then concentrated using a rotary evaporator at a temperature not exceeding 400 °C. The concentrate was then heated over a temperature-regulated water bath pre-set at 40 °C to obtain a solvent-free extract. The extract thus obtained was stored in the refrigerator at 4°C until use for Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometer analysis (Amole and Ilori, 2010).

Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometer (GC-MS) Analysis of the Bioactive Compounds

The bioactive compounds present in the ethanolic and aqueous leaf, stem bark, and root extracts of *Alstonia booei* were determined and identified by Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometer analytical

methods. The Agilent 6890 series GC-MS equipment was used for this analysis following the procedures described by Eswaraiah *et al.* (2019). The equipment had an HP-5MS column mass spectrometer operated at an initial column temperature of 30°C and heated up to 300°C at the rate of an increase of 10°C/min and maintained for 10 min. The injection port temperature was ensured at 250°C, and the Helium flow rate at 1.5 ml/min. The ionization voltage was 70 eV. The samples were injected in split mode of 10:1. Mass spectral scan range was set at 40-700 m/z. The ion source temperature was maintained at 230°C, and the Interface temperature was set at 240°C. The MS start time was 3 minutes, and the end time was 40 minutes, with a solvent cut time of 3 minutes. The identification of the compounds was done based on retention time, integral area of peaks, and by using the database of the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST). The similarity of compounds matched with >70% listing based on the NIST 59 library search (Imam *et al.*, 2017). The most active isolated compounds thus analysed and identified were stored in the refrigerator at 4 °C until use for antimalarial tests.

Animals for the Study

BALB/c mice of both sexes were used for this study. They were obtained from the Animal Department, Nigerian Institute of Pharmaceutical Research and Development, Idu, Abuja, Nigeria. Animal handling and care followed the National Institute of Health (NIH) Guide for Care and Use of Laboratory Animals. All protocols were approved by the University of Nigeria, Nsukka Animal Care and Use Committee with approval number UNN/ZEB/22/6553.

Plasmodium Parasite for the Study

The parasite used for this study is the *Plasmodium berghei* NK65 strain, which was sensitive to mefloquine. The parasite was obtained from the Animal Department, Nigerian Institute of Pharmaceutical Research and Development, Idu, Abuja, Nigeria.

Malaria Prophylaxis Tests of the Bioactive Compounds

Antimalarial tests were carried out on the bioactive compounds to determine their malaria prophylaxis effects against infections of *Plasmodium berghei* in BALB/c mice using procedures described by Lestari *et al.* (2023) with some modifications. On the first day, a set of mice of both sexes were randomly selected and administered orally with 100, 200, and 400 mg/kg body weight of the bioactive compounds separately using corn meal as the vehicle. Another set of mice, the negative control, was given 5 ml kg⁻¹ distilled water, while another set of mice, the positive control,

was given 5 mg kg⁻¹ of mefloquine. Treatment was conducted for three consecutive days. On the fourth day, the mice were infected with 10⁷ *P. berghei*, and after 72 hours, blood was taken from the tail of each mouse and examined microscopically to determine the level of parasitemia suppression and recorded accordingly.

Statistical Analysis

The values obtained were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. The mean values of the parameters studied

were compared using one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at a 95% confidence interval, and separated using a Turkey-b post hoc comparison. Probability values of $p < 0.05$ were considered significant. Results were expressed as mean \pm standard error of mean (SEM).

RESULTS

The antimalarial tests on the bioactive compounds showed significant antimalarial prophylactic activity against *Plasmodium berghei* infection in Balb/c mice. The results of the tests are shown in Tables 1- 6.

Table 1: Prophylactic activity of 1,3,5-Triazine, 2-methylamino-4,6-bis(nonafluoro-tert-butyl) a compound from aqueous leaf extract of *A. boonei*, and mefloquine in mice infected with *Plasmodium berghei*

Treatments (ml kg ⁻¹)	Suppression (%)
Distilled water 5	0.00 \pm 0.00 ^a
Compound 100	25.93 \pm 0.58 ^b
Compound 200	51.22 \pm 0.64 ^c
Compound 400	59.99 \pm 0.58 ^d
Mefloquine 5	86.76 \pm 0.64 ^e

¹All values expressed as mean \pm standard error (\pm SE).

²Different superscript letters indicated significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in mean values among different treatments using Turkey's b *post hoc* comparison. The antimalarial tests showed that all the doses (100, 200,

and 400 mg/kg body weight) used produced significant ($p < 0.05$) dose-dependent prophylactic activity against the parasite infection in the treated mice.

Table 2: Prophylactic activity of androsta--2,4,16-triene-3,6,17-triol, tri-TMS, a compound from aqueous stem bark extract of *A. boonei*, and mefloquine in mice infected with *Plasmodium berghei*

Treatments (ml kg ⁻¹)	Suppression (%)
Distilled water 5	0.00 \pm 0.00 ^a
Compound 100	46.12 \pm 0.58 ^b
Compound 200	55.65 \pm 2.83 ^c
Compound 400	65.94 \pm 1.15 ^d
Mefloquine 5	90.48 \pm 1.21 ^e

¹All values expressed as mean \pm standard error (\pm SE).

²Different superscript letters indicated significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in mean values among different treatments using Turkey's b *post hoc* comparison. The antimalarial tests showed that all the doses (100, 200,

and 400 mg/kg body weight) used produced significant ($p < 0.05$) dose-dependent prophylactic activity against the parasite infection in the treated mice.

Table 3: Prophylactic activity of 1-Oxo-forskolin, a compound from aqueous root extract of *A. boonei*, and Mefloquine in mice infected with *Plasmodium berghei*

Treatments (ml kg ⁻¹)	Suppression (%)
Distilled water 5	0.00 \pm 0.00 ^a
E Compound 100	52.71 \pm 0.64 ^b
Compound 200	69.88 \pm 1.15 ^c
Compound 400	71.66 \pm 1.62 ^c
Mefloquine 5	93.44 \pm 1.41 ^d

¹All values expressed as mean \pm standard error (\pm SE).

²Different superscript letters indicated significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in mean values among different treatments using Turkey's *b post hoc* comparison. The

antimalarial tests showed that all the doses (100, 200, and 400mg/kg body weight) used produced significant ($p < 0.05$) dose-dependent prophylactic activity against the parasite infection in the treated mice.

Table 4: Prophylactic activity of Aldosterone, N-methoxy-tri-TMS, a compound from ethanolic leaf extract of *A. boonei*, and mefloquine in mice infected with *Plasmodium berghei*

Treatments (ml kg-1)	Suppression (%)
Distilled water 5	0.00 \pm 0.00 ^a
Compound 100	50.22 \pm 3.00 ^b
Compound 200	63.35 \pm 1.21 ^c
Compound 400	71.55 \pm 1.79 ^d
Mefloquine 5	94.68 \pm 0.52 ^e

¹All values expressed as mean \pm standard error (\pm SE).

²Different superscript letters indicated significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in mean values among different treatments using Turkey's *b post hoc* comparison. The antimalarial tests showed that all the doses (100, 200,

and 400 mg/kg body weight) used produced significant ($p < 0.05$) dose-dependent prophylactic activity against the parasite infection in the treated mice.

Table 5: Prophylactic activity of Hecogenin acetate, a compound from ethanolic stem bark extract of *A. boonei*, and mefloquine in mice infected with *Plasmodium berghei*

Treatments (ml kg-1)	Suppression (%)
Distilled water 5	0.00 \pm 0.00 ^a
Compound 100	38.79 \pm 1.21 ^b
Compound 200	50.77 \pm 1.62 ^c
Compound 400	64.22 \pm 1.28 ^d
Mefloquine 5	93.04 \pm 1.73 ^e

¹All values expressed as mean \pm standard error (\pm SE).

²Different superscript letters indicated significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in mean values among different treatments using Turkey's *b post hoc* comparison. The antimalarial tests showed that all the doses (100, 200,

and 400 mg/kg body weight) used produced significant ($p < 0.05$) dose-dependent prophylactic activity against the parasite infection in the treated mice.

Table 6: Prophylactic activity of β -Dithiodilactic acid, a compound from ethanolic root extract of *A. boonei*, and mefloquine in mice infected with *Plasmodium berghei*

Treatments(mlkg ⁻¹)	Suppression (%)
Distilled water 5	0.00 \pm 0.00 ^a
Compound 100	30.11 \pm 1.83 ^b
Compound 200	49.60 \pm 0.46 ^c
Compound 400	56.98 \pm 1.73 ^d
Mefloquine 5	94.15 \pm 1.21 ^e

¹All values expressed as mean \pm standard error (\pm SE).

²Different superscript letters indicated significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in mean values among different treatments using Turkey's *b post hoc* comparison. The antimalarial tests showed that all the doses (100, 200,

and 400 mg/kg body weight) used produced significant ($p < 0.05$) dose-dependent prophylactic activity against the parasite infection in the treated mice.

DISCUSSION

Analysis of the bioactive compounds from the extracts showed that they belong to different classes of

compounds, including phenols, alkaloids, carboxylic acids, terpenes, acridones, and lactones. Similar to the findings from this study, several bioactive compounds have been found in plants such as phenols, alkaloids

(Babatunde, 2017), carboxylic acids (Imam *et al.*, 2017), glycosides, terpenes (Olanlokun *et al.*, 2021; Farooqi *et al.*, 2024), tannins, saponins (Uzor *et al.*, 2020), diterpenoids (Saleh *et al.*, 2019), acridones, and lactones (Rafiq *et al.*, 2024). Other studies on bioactive compounds of other plants also revealed the presence of other classes of bioactive compounds as also obtained in this study comprising carboxylic acids (Wong *et al.*, 2021), acridones (Winter, 2006), diosgenin (Omonirri *et al.*, 2021) and lactones (Chea *et al.*, 2006). Antimalarial tests were carried out on the bioactive compounds from the extracts to determine their prophylaxis antimalarial activity. The antimalarial tests showed that all the doses (100, 200, and 400 mg/kg body weight) used produced significant ($p < 0.05$) dose-dependent prophylactic effect against *P. berghei* parasite infection in the treated mice.

The prophylactic activity of 1,3,5-Triazine, 2-methylamino-4,6-bis(nonafluoro-tert-butyl), a methoxymethylbutyl class compound from aqueous leaf extract of *A. boonei*, revealed that the minimal prophylactic effect was found in the lowest administered dose of 100 mg/kg body weight while the optimal prophylactic effect was in the highest administered dose of 400 mg/kg body weight. In a similar study on methoxymethylbutyl class compound, Wong *et al.* (2021) evaluated chemical constituents from the crude extract of *Dendrocalamus asper* using chromatographic methods for their antimalarial potential, and of all the chemicals tested, dimethyl-15,16-dibutoxytricon-11,13,17,19-tetraenedioate, methoxyl-4-hydroxybenzoate, and 1-methoxy-4-(methoxymethyl)benzoate showed promising antimalarial activity.

In the prophylactic activity of androsta--2,4,16-triene-3,6,17-triol, tri-TMS, a lactone class compound from aqueous stem bark extract of *A. boonei*, it showed that the minimal prophylactic effect was found in the lowest administered dose of 100 mg/kg body weight while the optimal prophylactic effect was in the highest administered dose of 400 mg/kg body weight. Other similar studies have reported the antimalarial effects of lactones from plants. Chea *et al.* (2006), in their study, found that lactones possess antimalarial activity. They tested three lactones, and two of the compounds exhibited significant antimalarial activity. The result from the prophylactic test of 1-Oxo-forskolin, a diterpenoid compound from aqueous root extract of *A. boonei*, revealed that the lowest prophylactic effect was in the lowest administered dose of 100 mg/kg body weight, while the highest prophylactic effect was in the highest administered dose of 400 mg/kg body weight. Saleh *et al.* (2019)

carried out a study on the therapeutic potential of the Labdane Diterpenoid Forskolin and also recorded a significant antimalarial activity by the compound, which agrees with this result.

The prophylactic activity of Aldosterone, N-methoxy-tri-TMS, an acridone class compound from ethanolic leaf extract of *A. boonei*, showed that the lowest prophylactic effect was found in the lowest administered dose of 100 mg/kg body weight, while the highest prophylactic effect was in the highest administered dose of 400 mg/kg body weight. Winter *et al.* (2006) reported significant antimalarial activity of acridone compounds.

In the prophylactic activity of Hecogenin acetate, a diosgenin compound from ethanolic stem bark extract of *A. boonei*, it was revealed that the lowest prophylactic effect was found in the lowest administered dose of 100mg/kg body weight while the highest prophylactic effect was in the highest administered dose of 400mg/kg body weight. Omonirri *et al.* (2021) studied the antimalarial activity of diosgenin compound and reported that the compound exerted significant antimalarial activity on the tested murine model, which is akin to the result of this study.

The result of prophylactic test of Dithiodilactic acid, a compound from ethanolic root extract of *A. boonei*, revealed that the lowest prophylactic effect was in the lowest administered dose of 100mg/kg body weight while the highest prophylactic effect was in the highest administered dose of 400mg/kg body weight which corresponds to the results of the other prophylactic antimalarial tests in this study.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The antimalarial tests conducted in this study demonstrated that the bioactive compounds provided significant dose-dependent prophylaxis against malaria parasite infection in mice treated with *Plasmodium berghei*. Therefore, these bioactive compounds warrant further investigation and should be considered for the development of novel antimalarial drugs. Further studies should include tests on human malaria parasite isolates (specifically *Plasmodium falciparum*) as well as pharmacological assessments, pharmacokinetic evaluations, analysis of their modes of action, determination of appropriate dosage, and exploration of potential interactions with other drug formulations.

Ethical Approval

Animal handling and care followed the NIH Guide for Care and Use of Laboratory Animals. Protocols were approved by the University of Nigeria, Nsukka Animal Care and Use Committee.

Authors' contributions

Otuu, C. A., and Obiezue, R. N. N. conceptualized the study, planned, and designed all experiments. Udeh, E. O, Eke, S. S., and Usman-Yamman, H performed the formal analysis and all statistical analysis. Ekuma, I. C, Nwosu, C. G., and Otuu, A. Q. A. wrote the main manuscript text and performed the project administration. All authors reviewed the manuscript. All authors listed have made a substantial direct and intellectual contribution to this work and approved it for publication.

Funding

No funding was received for this study.

Availability of data and materials

The raw data and any materials supporting the conclusions of this article will be made available by the authors, without undue reservation, to any qualified researcher. used or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on request.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that there are no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank the Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology, University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Enugu State, Nigeria, for the use of their botanist experts in the identification and authentication of the plant materials used for this study. We would like to acknowledge the Animal Department, Nigerian Institute of Pharmaceutical Research and Development, Idu, Abuja, Nigeria, as the source of the animals and *Plasmodium berghei* parasite used in this study. We would also like to especially thank the Department of Zoology and Environmental Biology, University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Enugu State, Nigeria, for making their Animal house and Research laboratory available for us throughout the duration of this study.

REFERENCES

Afolabi, O.J. and Abejide, A.E. (2020). Antiplasmodial activities of *Morinda lucida* (Benth) and *Alstonia boonei* (De wild) in mice infected with *Plasmodium berghei*. *Bulletin of the Natural Research Center*, 44: 85–91.

- Amole, O.O. and Ilori, O.O. (2010). Antimicrobial activity of the aqueous and ethanolic extracts of the stem bark of *Alstonia boonei*. *International Journal of Pharmacology*, 1: 119–123.
- Arise, R.O., Malomo, S. O. and Lawal, M.M. (2012). Comparative antimalarial and toxicological effects of *artemisinin* with methanolic extract of *Carica papaya* leaves and bark of *Alstonia boonei* in animal models. *Advances in Natural and Applied Sciences*, 6: 116–123.
- Babatunde, O. (2017). GC-MS analysis of leaf, stem-bark, and root extracts of *Alstonia boonei*. *African Journal of Pharm. Pharmacology*, 12: 577–581.
- Chea, A., Hout, S., Long, C., Marcourt, L., Faure, R., Azas, N. and Elias, R. (2006). Antimalarial Activity of Sesquiterpene Lactones from *Vernonia cinerea*. *Chemical and Pharmaceutical Bulletin*, 54: 1437–1439.
- Eswaraiah, G., Peele, K.A., Krupanidhi, S., Indira, M., Kumar, R.B. and Venkateswarulu, T.C. (2019). GC-MS analysis for compounds identification in leaf extract of *Lumnitzera racemosa* and evaluation of its *in vitro* anticancer effect against MCF7 and Hela cell lines. *Journal of King Saud University of Science*, 32: 780–783.
- Farooqi, S.S., Naveed, S., Quamar, F., Sana, A., Farooqi, S.H., Sabir, N., Mansoor, A. and Sadir, H. (2024). Phytochemical analysis, GC-MS characterization and antioxidant activity of *Hordeum vulgare* seed extract. *Heliyon*, 10: e27297.
- Imam, A.A., Atiku, M.K., Muhammad, I.U., Ezema, M.D., Alhassan, A.J. and Alexander, I. (2017). *In vitro* Antimalarial Activity of Solvent Extracts of *Alstonia boonei* Stem Bark and Partial Characterization of Most Active Extract(s). *Journal of Pharmaceutical Research International*, 19: 1–10.
- Imieje, V.O. and Amafile, L.N. (2025). GC-MS Profiling, *In Vitro* Antimalarial, and Antimicrobial Activity of *Ricinodendron heudelotii* Seed Extracts. *Science of Phytochemistry*, 1: 1–8.
- Lestari, E., Setyaningrum, E., Wahyuningsih, S., Rosa, E., Nurcahyani, N. and Kanedi, M. (2023). Antimalarial tests and GC-MS analysis of ethanol and ethyl acetate extract of snake plant (*Sansevieria trifasciata* Prainj). *World Journal of Biological, Pharmaceutical and Health Sciences*, 15: 91–97.

- Madhiri, R. and Vijayalakshini, G. (2018). A Review of Phytochemical Composition and Pharmacological Aspects of the Genus *Alstonia*. *Pharma Tutor*, 6: 50–55.
- Muhseen, Z.T., Hameed, A.R., Al – Bhadly, O., Ahmad, S. and Li, G. (2021). Natural products for the treatment of *Plasmodium falciparum* malaria: An integrated computational approach. *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, 134: 104415.
- Nanven, A.F., Nannim, N., Monday, E.A., Mark, S., Wilson, N.B. and Anthony, D. (2024). Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry Analysis and Antimalarial Activity of *Salix ledermanni* ethanol leaves extracts. *Tropical Journal of Natural Product Research*, 8: 9121–9130.
- Ogbuehi, I.H. and Ebong, O.O. (2015). Traditional medicine treatment of malaria in Onitsha, South East Nigeria. *Greener Journal of Medical Science*, 5: 1–18.
- Olanlokun, J.O., Olowofolahan, A.O., Bodede, O., Adegbuyi, A.T., Princlloo, G., Steenkamp, P. and Olorunsogo, O.O. (2021). Anti-inflammatory potential of the n-hexane fraction of *Alstonia boonei* stem bark in Lipopolysaccharide-induced inflammation in Wistar rats. *Journal of Inflammatory Research*, 14: 3905–3920.
- Omonirri, M.A., Madubuogwu, N.U., Oraekei, D.I., Ataihire, J.U., Ofili, C.C. and Mbata, U.C. (2021). Antimalarial and hypoglycemic activities of diosgenin on alloxan-induced diabetic Wistar rats. *GSC Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 15: 73–79.
- Rafiq, M., Javaid, A., Kanwal, A., Anwar, A., Khan, I.H., Cheng, C. and Kawal, Q. (2024). GC-MS analysis and antifungal potential of flower extract of *Acacia nilotica subsp. Indica* against *Macrophomina phaseolina*. *Microbes and Pathogens*, 194: 106819.
- Saleh, B., Staniak, M., Czopek, K., Stepien, A., Dua, K. and Sharifi-Rad, J. (2019). The therapeutic potential of the Labdane Diterpenoid Forskolol. *Applied Science*, 9: 4089.
- Uzor, P.F., Prasasty, V.D. and Agubata, C.O. (2020). Natural Products as Sources of Antimalarial Drugs. *Evidence – Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, volume 2020: Article ID 8749083.
- Winter, R.W., Kelly, J.X., Smikstein, M.J., Dodean, R. and Bagby, G.C. (2006). Evaluation and lead optimization of antimalarial acridones. *Experimental Parasitology*, 114: 47–56.
- Wong, K., Osman, H., Parumasivam, T., Abdullah, J., Hassan, M. and Azmi, M. (2021). Antimalarial Evaluation of the Chemical Constituents Isolated from *Dondrocalamus asper*. *Journal of the Turkish Chemical Society Section A*, 8: 995–1002.
- World Health Organization (WHO). (2012). Update on Artemisinin Resistance. Available at <http://www.who.int/malaria/publications/atoz/arupdate042012.Pdf/>. Accessed June 2024.
- World Health Organization (WHO). (2019). World Malaria Report 2019. World Health Organization, Geneva. Available at <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/9789241565721>. Accessed July 2024.